

Qualitative Systematic Review Protocol

Review Title:

The Experiences of Peers of Students with Special Educational Needs Educated in Inclusive Settings: A Qualitative Systematic Review Protocol

Authors

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Abstract

Objective: The aim of this systematic review is to explore the experiences of peers of students with special educational needs in inclusive educational settings.

Introduction: In education, inclusive practices aim to provide equal access to social, cultural and educational opportunities for all learners, respecting their individual abilities and needs. The perceptions of peers towards students with special needs play a significant role through the entire educational process and influence not only present experiences of all students, but also their future. The development of awareness regarding the needs of fellow students, along with the formation of attitudes and a hierarchy of values, is closely linked to experiences these learners have. A qualitative systematic review synthesizing findings based on peers' experiences can provide deeper insight into this issue and help identify and define factors that may contribute in practice to more effective inclusive education, the development of social relationships, and the improved quality of life for individuals with special educational needs.

Inclusion criteria: Qualitative studies involving experiences of peers of students/pupils with special educational needs educated together at any stage of inclusive school will be included in this review. There is not any limitation in terms of age, gender, sex, culture, socio-economic status or location.

Methods: This review will be conducted according to JBI methodology for qualitative systematic reviews and PRISMA 2020 statement. The search will be carried out in the following sources:

ERIC, APA PsycINFO, Scopus, Web of Science Core Collection, PubMed, ProQuest, Central, ProQuest Dissertations & Theses, Open Dissertations, and Google Scholar (first 100 records). Screening, data extraction, and data synthesis will be conducted by two independent reviewers. The quality assessment of the evidence will use the ConQual approach.

Results: Results will be described in both narrative and tabular form.

Conclusions: The findings will be summarized and recommendations for practice and further research will be provided based on data synthesized findings.

Key words

experiences, peers, students with special educational needs/SEN, inclusive education, inclusion

Review Question/Objective

The objective of this review is to synthesize the evidence on experiences of peers of students with special educational needs educated in inclusive educational settings.

The objective will be achieved through five specific sub-steps:

- To systematically identify and synthesize existing empirical research exploring experiences of peers of students with special educational needs educated in inclusive educational settings.
- To critically appraise the methodological quality and trustworthiness of the included studies, with particular attention to study design, data collection, analyses and interpretation of the results.
- To identify and interpret recurring themes and patterns in the reported experiences of typically developing peers and assess the consistency and divergence across studies.
- To evaluate the meaningfulness and contextual relevance of findings as presented by study authors, including the adequacy of their interpretations in relation to the data (presence of relevant illustrations).
- To assess the implications and appropriateness of study conclusions in terms of their contribution to understanding inclusive education practices and peer dynamics.

Review Question: *“What are the Experiences of Peers of Students with Special Needs Educated in Inclusive Settings?”*

The review question follows the PICo (Participants, Phenomena of interest, Context) framework for qualitative research:

P - Peers of Students with Special Needs

I - Experiences

Co - Inclusive Educational Settings

Background

Inclusive education is a key goal of education reforms worldwide, driven by laws (Ainscow et al., 2019, Mariga et al., 2014), policies (Kleinhammer-Tramill, 2012, Swaffield, 2019), advocacy (Burke, 2015), and growing social awareness (Baglieri, 2012). It is a philosophical belief about the purposes of education and what “school systems, schools and classrooms should accomplish” (Goransson & Nilholm, 2014, p. 266).

The concept of inclusive education (IE) was defined in notably different ways by various authors (Booth and Ainscow, 2011; Fredrickson & Cline, 2009; Florian, 2019; Goransson & Nilholm, 2014; Norwich, 2013), but they were mostly attributed to the Salamanca Statement (UNESCO, 1994) and connected to the “Education For All” (EFA) movements (UNESCO, 1990). This movement called on the international community to reform educational systems that segregated, marginalized, or excluded students with SEN from accessing mainstream education. It promoted equal access to the same general education opportunities provided to non-disabled students (Florian, 2019; Kozleski et al., 2014, Norwich, 2013; Thomas & Loxley, 2022). All students, regardless of their social characteristics or learning differences, have the right to high quality education and to be valued and integral members of school communities (Ainscow & Cesar, 2006; Goransson & Nilholm, 2014). Notwithstanding various definitions of IE, there is a shared agreement on key philosophical principles. Education and schooling are seen as crucial in addressing social exclusion rooted in societal, structural, and institutional inequalities (Florian, 2014, Peters & Oliver, 2009). They should promote social justice (Artiles et al., 2020, Gerrard, 1994) and serve as a platform for building a more just society (Ainscow & Cesar, 2006).

IE is informed by the *social model of disability* (Skrtic, 1995; Naraian & Schlessinger, 2017; Shakespeare, 2006; Ware, 2010), which understands disability not as an individual deficit or impairment, as traditionally framed by the medical model. It is conceptualised as the result of systemic, environmental, and attitudinal barriers that prevent people with disabilities from full participation in society. From this perspective, "disablement" arises when environments are not accessible, inclusive, or equitably designed to meet the diverse needs of all individuals (Naraian & Schlessinger, 2017, Slee, R. & Allen, J., 2001).

A truly inclusive educational environment depends not only on structural and instructional support but also on fostering positive attitudes, empathy, and a sense of belonging among all students, including peers of learners with special educational needs (Dewsbury et al., 2019, Fu et al., 2022, Lin et al., 2025). Promoting understanding, respect, and solidarity within the classroom helps create a learning space where every student feels valued and supported (Dağlı Gökbulut, 2024, Grindal et al., 2016, Lin et al., 2025).

At the same time, it is essential to ensure that support for students with special educational needs does not come at the expense of others, and that inclusion is seen as beneficial for everyone (Fletcher, 2008, Molina et al., 2021, O'Connor, 2023). The aim of IE is not to lower standards, but to create flexible, responsive approaches that allow *every learner*—with or without identified needs—to thrive and grow together in a shared educational environment (All belong, 2025, Florian, 2024)

While educational research (both qualitative and quantitative) often focuses on the perspectives of teachers (Rix et al., 2006) or parents (Paseka & Schwab, 2019, Hodges et al., 2020, Benson et al., 2024), and increasingly also on students with special educational needs (SEN) themselves (Sedláčková et al., 2025, Messiou, 2019) in recent years, it is equally important to consider the voices of peers of students with SEN (Dağlı Gökbulut, 2024). Peers share the inclusive classrooms, contribute to the class climate, and have their own educational and social needs that should be addressed (Barth & Grutter, 2024, Chung & Douglas, 2022). The dynamics of diverse classes—shaped by teacher approaches and student relationships—require attention. Understanding experiences with IE (Cook et al., 2010) and learning from the experiences of all participants of the educational process helps to ensure that inclusive education is effective and beneficial for everyone, supports social development, and fosters values aligned with current societal goals (Booth & Ainscow, 2011). Systematic reviews of qualitative studies play a vital role by providing evidence to guide policy and practice (Lockwood et al., 2020), generating insights and topics for future quantitative research, and contributing to exploring the values and preferences of users that belong to the key characteristics of evidence-based practice. The findings can guide the implementation of supportive systems, personalized teachers' guidance, as well as peer collaboration (Valera, 2024), promoting well-being and success of all students.

A systematic review focusing on the experiences of peers of students with special educational needs can provide valuable insight into inclusive education from a different perspective and offer information that may help to develop more effective strategies for fostering positive peer relationships, enhancing classroom climate, and promoting a sense of belonging for all students (Asakaviciute, 2024, Fletcher, 2008). We have identified one scoping and one systematic review dealing with similar issue - with peers of students with special needs. Nevertheless, the scoping review addresses only a single subgroup of peers of students with special needs - peers of students with physical disabilities (Edwards et al., 2019), which limits its depth and applicability in understanding real-world perspectives, and provides only a broad overview of the existing literature without critically appraising or synthesizing the findings in depth. And, although the existing systematic review meets requirements on participants, it explored only the attitudes of students without disabilities toward peers with disabilities (Freer, 2021). Further more, both publications are relatively dated, and covered studies published between 2012 and 2019, so we believe that extending the scope to include the entire population of peers of students with any type of special educational needs (SEN)—and focusing not only on attitudes but also on lived experiences—could provide meaningful and up-to-date insights that enhance inclusive practices. Understanding how inclusion is perceived and experienced by classmates without identified special needs is essential for creating supportive, equitable, and socially cohesive learning environments (Hammer, 2017, Freer, 2021).

Inclusion/Exclusion Criteria

Types of participants

This qualitative review will consider studies that include typically developing students educated in inclusive educational settings who are the fellow students/classmates/schoolmates/peers of students/pupils with special educational needs/SEN. Studies focusing only on students with SEN will be excluded.

Types of phenomena of interest

This qualitative review will consider studies that investigate personal experience/lived experience of typically developing students educated in inclusive educational settings. The focus of the research will deal with peer interactions, social/emotional development, or perceptions or other personal experience of these students.

Type of context

This qualitative review will consider studies that investigate students' experience at any inclusive educational settings (preschool, primary, secondary or higher education). Studies that deal with school integration and mainstreaming will also be included. Medical or clinical interventions without educational context will be excluded.

Types of studies

This qualitative systematic review will consider studies that contain qualitative data including, but not limited to, designs such as phenomenology, grounded theory, ethnography, action research and feminist research. The texts such as opinion papers and reports will not be considered. The review will exclude expert opinions, discussion papers, and position papers. Conference abstracts will also be excluded. Included will be qualitative studies or mixed methods studies if the qualitative can be extracted. Quantitative studies will be excluded.

Search strategy

The search strategy aims to find published and unpublished studies. A three-step search strategy will be utilized in this review. An initial limited search of EDS multi search engine will be undertaken followed by the analyses of the words contained in the title and abstract, and the index terms used to describe the article. A secondary search using all identified keywords and index terms will then be undertaken across all included databases and information sources. Thirdly, the reference lists of all relevant reports and articles will be searched for additional studies. Studies published in English, Czech or Slovak will be considered for inclusion in this review. All studies, regardless of publication date, will be considered for inclusion in this review.

The databases to be searched:

- **ERIC (Education Resources Information Center)**
- **APA PsycINFO**
- **Scopus**
- **Web of Science Core Collection**
- **PubMed** (for developmental or behavioral aspects)
- **ProQuest Central**

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The search for unpublished studies/grey literature will include: grey literature databases (**Google Scholar**), dissertations (**Open Dissertations, ProQuest Dissertations & Theses, Theses.cz**),

After the search, all identified citations will be collated and uploaded into Rayyan (Ouzzani et al., 2016) and duplicates will be removed. Titles and abstracts will be screened by two independent reviewers for assessment against the eligibility criteria for the review (pilot screening of at least 100 titles/abstracts by the same reviewers will have preceded the formal screening). Potentially relevant studies will be retrieved in full into the JBI System for the Unified Management, Assessment and Review of Information (JBI SUMARI, Adelaide, Australia) (Munn et al., 2019) and included in the reference list. Additionally, the full texts of selected papers will be assessed in detail against the eligibility criteria by two independent reviewers. The reasons for exclusion of studies that will not meet the eligibility criteria on the basis of reading full texts will be attached in the Appendix. Any disagreements that will arise between the reviewers at each stage of the study selection process will be resolved through discussion, or with another reviewer. The process of study selection will be described in Figure 1, PRISMA flow diagram (Page et al., 2021).

Initial keywords to be used will be following (Table 1, see strings in Appendix B):

Table 1: Key Concepts and Keywords

Key Concept	Keywords / Synonyms / Related Terms
Peers of students with special needs	peers, classmates, fellow students, schoolmates, typically developing students, general education students, intact students
Students with special needs	special needs, SEN, special educational needs, disabilit*, disorders, impairments, learning disabilit*, developmental disabili*, autism, autism spectrum disorder, autistic spectrum disorder, Asperger, intellectual disabilit*
Inclusive education	inclusive education, inclusive school*, mainstream school*, integration, integrated/integrative/inclusive classroom*, inclusive classes, inclusive settings, inclusion
Experience*	experience, lived experience*, personal experience*, perception*, attitude*, view*, opinion*, interaction*, social experience*

Figure 1:

PRISMA 2020 flow diagram for new systematic reviews which included searches of databases, registers and other sources

*Consider, if feasible to do so, reporting the number of records identified from each database or register searched (rather than the total number across all databases/registers).
 **If automation tools were used, indicate how many records were excluded by a human and how many were excluded by automation tools.

Source: Page MJ, et al. BMJ 2021;372:n71. doi: 10.1136/bmj.n71.

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Data Extraction

Qualitative data will be extracted from papers included in the review using the author-developed data extraction tool according to standardized data extraction tool JBI-QARI (Zhang & Cai, 2023) (Appendix A). The extraction will be done by two independent reviewers. The data extracted will include specific details about the study, methods, population, phenomena of interest, context, outcomes of significance to the review question and specific objectives. The information about the research ethics, the researcher and researchers' impact on the research will also be extracted.

The items in the extraction table (see also the table in Appendix A):

The study details: The first author, year of publication and the full reference.

Methods: Philosophical background, research question, research methods for data collection and analyses.

Population: number of participants, students' age/school grade, gender, nationality, language, socio-economic status.

Phenomena of interest: Experiences - how is experience defined/perceived by the authors.

Context: type of school, geographical context (*urban, suburban, rural*), cultural context, special needs or diagnoses of schoolmates/classmates/peers with special educational needs, number of schoolmates with special educational needs per class.

Study outcomes: Themes of narrative description.

Ethics: presence of the informed consent, ethics committee

The presence of information about the researcher and researcher's impact on the research.

Data syntheses

The findings from the included studies will be analyzed using the JBI SUMARI software. The studies results will be used without altering the original interpretation provided by the authors of each study. Each theme or narrative interpretation of the findings will be accompanied by a direct quotation from the study participants, and only those findings that are sufficiently supported by such quotations will be included. Individual findings will be categorized and subsequently synthesized into synthesized findings, which may then serve as a basis or inspiration for informing pedagogical practice and inclusive education policy.

The assessment of methodological quality

Qualitative papers selected for retrieval will be assessed by two independent reviewers for authenticity prior to inclusion in the review using standardized Joanna Bridge Institute Qualitative Assessment and Review Instrument (JBI-QUARI) (Appendix I). Any disagreements that arise between the reviewers will be resolved through discussion, or with the third reviewer.

All synthesized findings will be assessed via the ConQual approach (Munn et al., 2014), developed by JBI (former Joanna Brigg Institute) to determine the degree of certainty in the conclusions drawn from qualitative evidence synthesis. ConQual enables the assessment of two key elements: *dependability*, which pertains to the methodological rigor of the included studies as determined by the JBI Critical Appraisal Checklist for Qualitative Research; and *credibility*, which concerns the alignment between the researchers' interpretations and the supporting data. (Lockwood et al., 2024).

Dependability will be assessed using five items from the JBI Critical Appraisal Checklist for Qualitative Research (Lockwood et al., 2015). These include assessing the alignment between the research methodology and the research questions, data collection methods, and data analysis. Additionally, the appraisal considers whether the researcher's cultural or theoretical positioning is clearly stated and whether the reciprocal influence between the researcher and the research is addressed. Assessing dependability in JBI systematic reviews of qualitative research will follow the recommended ranking system (Lockwood et al., 2024):

- If 4–5 items on the JBI Critical Appraisal Checklist are rated 'yes', the dependability rating will remain unchanged.
- If 2–3 items are rated 'yes', the rating will be downgraded by one level.
- If only 0–1 items are rated 'yes', the rating will be downgraded by two levels.

Assessing credibility in JBI systematic reviews of qualitative research will follow the recommended ranking system (Lockwood et al., 2024):

- Findings supported by an illustration that is beyond reasonable doubt will be signed as U - Unequivocal
- Findings supported by an illustration that lacks clear association will be signed as C - Credible
- Findings not supported by any illustration will be signed as U - Unsupported

The credibility ranking system (Lockwood et al., 2024) will be applied as follows:

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- No downgrade will be applied if only unequivocal findings are included.
- Downgrade by 1 level – if findings include a mix of unequivocal and credible evidence.
- Downgrade by 2 levels – if all findings are credible.
- Downgrade by 3 levels – if findings include a mix of credible and unsupported evidence.
- Downgrade by 4 levels – if all findings are unsupported.

Each synthesized finding will begin with a high confidence rating, which may be downgraded based on dependability and credibility. The final ConQual score (high, moderate, low, or very low) will be presented in a Summary of Findings table, helping inform decisions in education and practice.

Discussion

This qualitative systematic review protocol outlines a plan to synthesize existing evidence on experiences of peers of students with SEN educated in inclusive educational settings. As the inclusive trends continue to grow globally, understanding the lived experiences of these students is essential for informing education policy and practice, as well as support service delivery.

We expect the systematic review to provide in-depth insights into the contextual challenges, facilitators, and coping strategies associated with inclusive education, which can help to build mutual friendships, a positive school climate, and lead to the creation of a student community where pupils are considerate of each other, support one another, show understanding toward others, are able to empathize with their situations, and where inclusive education enriches everyone involved.

Strength and limitations

One of the key strengths of this protocol and the planned systematic review lies in the use of a transparent and rigorous methodology. We will follow the JBI (former Joanna Briggs Institute) approach for qualitative synthesis and adhere to the Enhancing Transparency in Reporting the Synthesis of Qualitative Research (ENTREQ) (Tong et al., 2012) and Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic review and Meta-Analysis Protocols (PRISMA-P) (Moher et al., 2015) reporting guidelines. A comprehensive search strategy will be applied across multiple databases, and study selection, quality appraisal, and data synthesis will be conducted independently by two reviewers to minimize bias and enhance credibility.

However, potential limitations must be acknowledged. First, the language limitation to inclusion of only English or Czech language studies may cause language bias and omission of relevant studies published in other languages. The number of eligible studies may be reduced, potentially limiting the comprehensiveness and cultural diversity of the synthesis. Second, qualitative research is inherently context-dependent, and variations in educational systems and sociocultural settings may affect the transferability of the synthesized findings. Third, as with all reviews of published literature, the quality and depth of reporting in the original studies may influence the robustness of the synthesis.

Despite these limitations, the findings of this review are expected to contribute valuable knowledge to the field by synthesizing diverse perspectives and identifying gaps in the literature. It will also

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provide a foundation for future empirical research and offer practical insights for teacher training programs aiming to support inclusive practices at schools.

Conflicts of interest

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the authors.

Author contributions

DS: Supervision, Writing – original draft, Conceptualization, Methodology, Project administration.
LB: Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing. AS: Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – original draft. JD: Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – original draft. JK: Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Project administration, Methodology, Writing – review & editing. ZS: Conducting search strategy, Search.

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Will be completed later

Generative AI statement

The author(s) declare that Generative AI was not used during the creation of this manuscript.

Supplementary material

Appendix A: The Data Extraction Table

Appendix B: Search strategy

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Appendix A

The Data Extraction Table

Data Extraction Table		Study No 1
Study details	The 1st author's name	
	Year of publication	
	Reference	
Ethics	Presence of the ethic board permission	
	Informed consent	
Researchers	Information about the researchers	
	The impact of researches on the research	
Methods	Philosophical background	
	Research question/objective	
	Data collection	
	Data analyses	
Population	Number of participants	
	Age/school grade	
	Gender	
	Nationality/language	
	Socio-economic status	
Phenomena of interest	How is experience defined by the authors	
Context	Type of school	
	Geographical context (country + urban, suburban, rural)	
	Type or level of special needs or diagnoses of schoolmates with SEN	
	Number of schoolmates with SEN per class	
Study outcomes	Themes	
	Narrative description of results	

Appendix B: Search strategy

STRINGS:

(peer? OR classmate? OR “fellow students” OR schoolmate? OR “typically developing student?” OR “general education student?” OR “intact student?”)

AND

(“special needs” OR SEN OR “special educational needs” OR disabilit* OR disorder* OR impairment* OR “learning disabilit*” OR “developmental disabilit*” OR autism OR ASD OR „autism spectrum disorder*“ OR „autistic spectrum disorder*“ OR Asperger* OR “intellectual disabilit*”)

AND

(“inclusive education” OR “inclusive school*” OR “mainstream school*” OR integration OR integrated OR integrative OR “inclusive classroom*” OR “inclusive classes” OR “inclusive settings” OR inclusion)

AND

(experience* OR “lived experience*” OR “personal experience*” OR perception* OR attitude* OR view? OR opinion* OR interaction* OR “social experience*”)

Example of search in ERIC (EBSCOhost)

Search was conducted on the 11th of June 2025 13:34-13:58 (CET)

1. (peer? (Title/Abstract) OR classmate? (Title/Abstract) OR “fellow student?”(Title/Abstract) OR schoolmate? (Title/Abstract) OR “typically developing student?” (Title/Abstract) OR “general education student?” (Title/Abstract) OR “intact student?” (Title/Abstract)) (71,532)
2. (“special needs”(Title/Abstract) OR SEN (Title/Abstract) OR “special educational needs” (Title/Abstract) OR disabilit* (Title/Abstract) OR disorder* (Title/Abstract) OR impairment* (Title/Abstract) OR “learning disabilit*” (Title/Abstract) OR “developmental disabilit*” (Title/Abstract) OR autism (Title/Abstract) OR ASD (Title/Abstract) OR „autism spectrum disorder*“ (Title/Abstract) OR „autistic spectrum disorder*“ (Title/Abstract) OR Asperger* (Title/Abstract) OR “intellectual disabilit*” (Title/Abstract) OR DE "Asperger Syndrome" (Subject Heading) OR DE "Intellectual Disability" (Subject Heading) OR DE "Autism" (Subject Heading) OR DE "Autism Spectrum Disorders" (Subject Heading) OR DE "Developmental Disabilities" (Subject Heading)) (121,239)
3. (“inclusive education”(Title/Abstract) OR “inclusive school*” (Title/Abstract) OR “mainstream school*” (Title/Abstract) OR integration (Title/Abstract) OR “inclusive classroom*” (Title/Abstract) OR “inclusive classes” (Title/Abstract) OR “inclusive settings” (Title/Abstract) OR inclusion (Title/Abstract) OR DE "Inclusive Education" (Subject Heading) OR DE "Inclusion" (Subject Heading)) (76,758)
4. (experience* (Title/Abstract) OR “lived experience*” (Title/Abstract) OR “personal experience*” (Title/Abstract) OR perception* (Title/Abstract) OR attitude* (Title/Abstract) OR view? (Title/Abstract) OR opinion* (Title/Abstract) OR interaction* (Title/Abstract) OR “social experience*” (Title/Abstract) OR DE "Experience" (Subject Heading)) (605,848)
5. 1 AND 2 AND 3 AND 4 (1,216)
6. **Reviewed: 842**

